

CREATION OF TECHNOLOGY FOR DETERMINING FOSSIL WEALTH IN THE DEPTHS OF THE EARTH USING SEISMOPRIYOMNIKS IN AN ARTIFICIAL MAGNETIC FIELD

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7411357>

ELSEVIER

Received: 03-12-2022

Accepted: 07-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

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Abstract: this article discusses the number of probes installed in a mine, their number, the recording of fluctuations in the wave field in them, as well as the recording of a full-wave vector of Multi-Channel (Ten-channel) seismoboulters placed in space.

Keywords: mine, number of probes, wave field, oscillations, multichannel, seismic, wave Vector, Space, fossil resources, artificial magnetic field.

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Introduction. Multi-channel x, y, z - seysmake-like fossil probes are used. The number of probes installed in the mine is not limited, fluctuations in the wave field in them are recorded. Therefore, the issue of recording a full wave vector of multichannel (ten-channel) seismobulners placed in space is considered relevant.

Creation of a new technology aimed at increasing high efficiency in geological exploration work in the field of Earth Sciences (geophysics and other)

-With the help of the SV-12-10 seismopriomnik, the characteristics of the magnetic field of a wide range formed by underground fossil resources are determined.

Discussion.

Photo 1. Overview of the seismopriyomnik device in a) vertical) horizontal position

To identify oil fields, an innovation project will be implemented to create modern technologies for seismopriyomniks in an artificial magnetic field.

The amplitude–frequency and phase characteristics of seismopriyomniks are determined. As an oscillating device, a type SV 12-10 seismobulder is used, which is attached to the Oscillator 3 spring.

Areas of application:

National economy and industrial enterprises, "Uzneftgazburgashlash" LLC, "Uzbekgeophysics" JSC and "Shurtanneftgaz" LLC are in oil and gas wells.

In recent years, seismic research has been carried out extensively in the interior of the environment, and it is important to carry out seismic research in the interior of the environment. To perform such work, it is necessary to carry out multi - channel x, y, z-seismic fossil probes. The number of probes installed in the mine is not limited, fluctuations in the wave field in them are recorded. Therefore, the issue of recording a full wave vector of multichannel (ten-channel) seismobulners placed in space is considered relevant.

As an oscillating device, a type SV 12-10 seismobulder is used, which is attached to the Oscillator 3 spring. This seismabulcator 4 connects to a seismabulcator placed in an artificial magnetic field of this type through a 60 cm tube with a massive length. In doing so, the artificial magnetic field is generated alternately using an electromagnet and a salenoid.

Device scheme

Oscillating device scheme (A),

*Scheme for obtaining amplitude - frequency characteristics of the seismobulder**Scheme for obtaining phase characteristics of a seismabulant*

In the output part of the amplitude - frequency characteristic of seismocabulants in an artificial magnetic field for determining oil fields

E.Yu.K is measured with a microvoltmeter and the appearance of the sinusoidal is controlled using an oscillograph.

With the oscillating SV-12-10 seismic, magnetic field characteristics of a wide range formed by underground fossil resources are determined. As a result, the efficiency of determining oil and gas fields is increased.

Conclusion: It has been contracted by the customer and contractor, and a special control chamber and temperature display device are installed to fully control the terms of the contract, allowing full control by the customer and contractor via Wi-Fi. To determine the oil fields, a device of an artificial magnetic field seismometer is installed. Based on the results of the analysis, it makes it possible to draw conclusions about the determination of oil and gas fields.

The oil and gas separator and mixture detection device will Jadd the drilling process and will be carried out without spending a lot of money.

Results of scientific research:

- amplitude-frequency and phase characteristics of seismopriomniks are determined;

-oscillating amplitude-frequency and phase characteristics in the medium are determined using the oscillating SV-12-10 seismopriyomnik;

- A new technology will be created aimed at increasing high efficiency in geological exploration work in the field of Earth Sciences (geophysics and other) ;

-With the help of the SV-12-10 seismopriomnik, the characteristics of the magnetic field of a wide range formed by underground fossil resources are determined.

Testing and implementation of the results: in the oil and gas industry will be introduced into practice at the enterprises of Shurtan Gas LLC, Uzneftgazkuduktamirlash JSC, Uzneftgazburgashlashlar LLC and Uzbekgeofizika JSC.

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